

NEWSLETTER #1

APRIL, 2023

COGNITIVE EDGE-CLOUD WITH SERVERLESS COMPUTING

EDGELESS project aims to leverage the serverless concept in all the layers in the edge-cloud continuum to fully benefit from diverse and decentralised computational resources available on-demand close to where data are produced or consumed. In particular, we aim at realising an efficient and transparent horizontal pooling of the resources on edge nodes with constrained capabilities or specialised hardware, smoothly integrated with cloud resources, which is a giant leap forward compared to state-of-the-art vertical offloading solutions where the edge is a mere supplement of the cloud.

CONSORTIUM

The project unites 12 partners from 6 European countries, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

[Check EDGELESS Consortium here >>](#)

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PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Enable efficient operation of data-intensive applications with a dynamic behaviour for the realisation of a cognitive framework spanning across the edge-cloud continuum, considering resource-constrained and heterogeneous edge computing resources under fast changing conditions

Develop cognitive tools and techniques for an efficient use of resources in networks of constrained and specialised edge nodes, taking into consideration computation needs and performance, always ensuring the most efficient implementation of function-oriented execution

Enable trusted access to lambda functions executed on edge nodes, including devices with limited computational capabilities, to enable a decentralised exchange of trusted data and computations, leveraging certified hardware security

Define interfaces and models to deploy edge applications in a continuum multi-provider environment according to specific functional and non-functional requirements, while ensuring the highest level of QoS

Evaluate the solution in a wide range of realistic use cases, with heterogeneous requirements

EDGELESS Use cases

Autonomous Smart City Surveillance

This Use-Case is driven to increase the safety of citizens by monitoring strategic geographical places through a city-wide distribution of CCTV cameras. The processing of data at the edge of the network has several advantages, particularly low latency and backhaul traffic reduction (OPEX bandwidth reduction), however providing new applications and services to be deployed on low-powered and widely distributed devices, with rather limited compute capabilities, raises specific challenges which otherwise would not occur in a classic centralised unified cloud computing solution.

Internet of Robotic Things

This Use-Case originates from the increasing demand for complex distributed systems capable of handling large-scale factory automation. The movement to customer-driven production and personalisation has generated a need for flexible manufacturing systems that can respond rapidly to production process variations

HealthCare Assistant

This Use-Case will advantage of ML capabilities, will provide people with special needs living at home (seniors, pre/post-surgery or chronic disease patients) with a personalised assistant that will help them in their daily life, monitor their health status and activities, and assist them in difficult situations.

First Quarter Highlights

KICK OFF MEETING – 24-25 JAN 2023, BARCELONA

On January 24-25, 2023, the EDGELESS consortium successfully held the kick-off meeting for their project in Barcelona, Spain.

[Read more here >>](#)

KEY FACTS

Title:	Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing
Acronym:	EDGELESS
GA No:	101092950
Start:	01 January 2023
End:	31 December 2025
Topic:	HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-02
Type of action:	HORIZON-RIA

Antonio Paradell

Message from the Project Coordinator

"I am very pleased that we are issuing today our first newsletter of the EDGELESS project. Our project aims to leverage the serverless concept in all the layers of the edge-cloud continuum, defining a new approach to the execution of edge applications based on the dynamic orchestration of serverless functions running on heterogeneous edge devices.

Our solution is aimed at addressing real challenges and it will be piloted and evaluated in a wide range of realistic use cases, from an Autonomous Smart City Surveillance that increases the safety of citizens, to an Internet of Robotic Things solution for complex distributed systems capable of handling large-scale factory automation, and to a HealthCare Assistant that provides a personalised assistant to people with special needs living at home.

We started this exciting and challenging initiative just four months ago, it is going to be a long three-years journey in which a team consisting of a perfect mix of European universities, research centres, high-tech SMEs and large industries are working together to take the best of these technologies, designing a solution that can meet the expectations of our pilot applications.

In this newsletter we are bringing to you our first thoughts, findings and developments, I hope that you will enjoy them."

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